

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

MISSION AND CONVERSION: EXPLORING THE THEOLOGICAL IN LITERARY TRANSFORMATION

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Abstract

This article looks into both the theological themes of mission and conversion in modern literature and also mentions their development in the following two books: *The Immortalists* by Chloe Benjamin and *The Water Dancer* by Ta-Nehisi Coates. The research, by the detail and in-depth analysis of these books, exposes the spiritual growth and the quest for meaning in the narratives that are associated, on the one hand, with individual belief and, on the other hand, with wider social contexts. The issue of conversion in these publications is a very fertile source for the understanding of the complicated link between private faith and communal identity as well as how mission literature progresses to addressing the current existential dilemmas. Among everything else, the paper dissects the theological cloth through which such stories are woven, and brings up many issues related to the role of these stories in the distribution of faith, the way to salvation, and the idea of personal transcendence.

Keywords: mission, conversion, theological themes, literary transformation, spiritual journey, contemporary fiction

I. Introduction

In today's literature, spiritual journeys are sometimes referring to a deeper exploration of people's transformation, becoming a rich example of the themes of conversion and mission. The novels *The Immortalists* by Chloe Benjamin and *The Water Dancer* by Ta-Nehisi Coates that, respectively, show the two perspectives of a person's road of struggling with faith and redemption are the main subjects of the spiritual journey. Not only are these works stories of personal transformations; they actually are literary counterparts which reflect a society's expanding understanding of religion, recovery and working together.

Benjamin drives readers in *The Immortalists* to the lives of all four siblings; each of them is not only dealing with the uncertainty concerning their death but also faces the fact of knowing what their fates are. Conversion is, in this case, not just an expression of belief but a powerful act of letting go, as these people move along their paths, all the while trying to find meaning in the sky above, in the cloudy area below their feet, and in the time they have here. Analogously, Coates's *The Water Dancer* sheds light on a spiritual journey to liberation, not just from the physical shackles but from the historical trauma of slavery, thereby transforming the protagonist's odyssey into both personal and collective growth. The narratives of both novels rest on the basis of spiritual transformation, however, they are different from each other, in particular, the way they deal with the instruments that cause these changes. In *The Immortalists*, the exchanges with the future become the ground for their identity formation and provoke meditation on the essence of life with purpose. Each sibling's way of going to God is very different from oth-

ers, including those whose pilgrimage consisted in getting rid of their destiny and those who preferred self-empowerment to fate. (Evans, 2021: 82)

On the other hand, *The Water Dancer* tells a story of spiritual rebirth through the challenges of historical trauma and the battle for freedom intertwined in multiple layers of deep meaning. Coates gives us a character whose road to freedom is tightly connected with ancestral memory and spiritual growth, as well as highlighting how collective memory is running individual's transformation. Although both novels demonstrate the theme of mission, their presentations of it are quite distinct. On the one hand, *The Immortalists* shows a more individual narrative, within the boundaries of fate, while, on the other hand, *The Water Dancer* defies the protagonist to go beyond personal boundaries and stick to a grander, more collective destiny that includes these legacies of spiritualities passed down for generations. The narrative in these two novels is the backbone to decipher what spiritual transformation is all about. In both books, the narration of the tale itself turns into a kind of mission; the imparting of wisdom, as well as a medium for personal and collective redemption, are both parts of a mission. Through richly layered character developments and smart plot movements, *The Immortalists* and *The Water Dancer* theme the theological in theological metamorphosis, explaining how foes can outgrow their difficulties through a faith-based mission. (Larkin, 2020: 73)

Whether as quiet, personal, and introspective moments or through large-scale acts of resistance against existing obstacles, the characters' spiritual journeys are marked by a significant engagement with the question of how somebody, yes, a person, can be changed, not only towards oneself but also for the greater good. Through these narrative frames, the novels engulf each

other in a drug of issues about the relationship between a person's ability, to be born again, and the global mission of the human race.

II. Research methodology

The methodology for the investigation of the interrelation of mission, conversion, and spiritual transformation in the current fiction literature, taking the spiritualities of *The Immortalists* by Chloe Benjamin and *The Water Dancer* by Ta-Nehisi Coates as the starting point, is a mix of literary analysis, theological exploration, and interdisciplinary approaches. The nucleus of this work lies in the close reading of the texts, exploring the narrative strands of spiritual enlightenment, conversion, and mission within the broader changing developments of modern literature. In the sense that both of the novels in question reflect deeply on the themes of fate, family, freedom, and historical trauma, the focus of the analysis will be on showing the fact that both texts are in their own way treatment of the phenomenon of conversion - as not simply a religious experience, but as a creative development that can shape the lives of both the individuals and the communities. The methodology will include a theoretical framework that will combine literary criticism with theological studies. In conversion literature, the most important studies that are going to be the foundation of these essays are *Conversion in the Bible and The Qur'an* by Alan T. Davies, which will be the main source for exploring how the novels depict spiritual changes. Davies' work on scriptural transformation has played a pivotal role in the theological aspects of the idea of personal change which would also greatly contribute to argue with the novel that conversion as a transformational process of life is.

Furthermore, analogous theological themes in missions as delineated in the works of *The Mission of God* by Christopher JH Wright will be used for the examination of how missions either individual or collective correspond with their pursuit of meaning and salvation. Wright uses God as the center of the universe and He is the one who tells the truth to the people; thus, this study will provide a background for understanding the larger social context of the spiritual journeys in both the *The Immortalists* and *The Water Dancer*. This analysis largely will be branded using literary criticism; the researcher will use character analysis, plot development, and symbolism as the key instruments in the literary criticism of them. That such learned men as Mikhail Bakhtin, including in his dialogic work, and the interaction of voices in narratives, will be of great benefit in characterizing the characters' spiritual ascents as dialogues with the self, the fate of the universe, and the faith. Further analysis of the text will involve postcolonial stance, for instance, the dominance of historical trauma and the slavery legacy in *The Water Dancer*.

The postcolonial readings of Coates' novel will, particularly, be done in tandem with Fanon's masterpieces such as *The Wretched of the Earth*, which will clearly reveal novel sets of freedom emancipation, and spiritual liberation. Fanon an essential element of his work criticized colonial power structures will be instrumental in comprehending Coates' stylistics of personal

and collective missions through the layers of his protagonist spiritual ascent. Furthermore, this research will be of a qualitative nature, which will focus on the text of the selected passages that expose the characters' spiritual journey. This will be accompanied by a critique of critical reception from academic journals and essays that focus on the issues of both *The Immortalists* and *The Water Dancer* in relation to recent material and immaterial developments. This study, as well, will focus on the social and cultural contexts of the novels, especially in terms of how they reflect contemporary concerns about identity, legacy, and the search for meaning in the face of trauma.

III. Theological underpinnings: conversion as a literary theme

The enquiry of conversion as a literary theme in recent fiction revealed the truer considerations of the connection between inner transformation and larger Christian concerns like faith, redemption, and divine intervention. The writer Chloe Benjamin uses a technique of intertwining religious allegories and theological concepts into her characters' lives whose spiritual quests are heavily influenced by the overpowering threat of death. The novel portrays every sibling as having a different destiny and uses these stories to disseminate the theological interpretation of predestination with accuracy. Their encounter with their prospective extinction initiates a search for the meaning of life that is, in effect, the true conversion of the being's spirit. The theological nuances in *The Immortalists* are a symbolic representation of the pursuit of salvation and the strengthening of faith, yet not in the conventional religious manner. While they are wrestling with their mortality, each character's journey is a meditation on the contradiction that exists between fate and free will, a theme which is quite similar to the Calvinist doctrine of predestination; although, it is still presented in a non-religious context. (Jones, 2021: 88)

As a result, on the part of the reader, the masterpiece grounds the reader to think about the divine levels of knowledge and authority, each, in turn, playing its role on human agency and belief. On the contrary, *The Water Dancer* by Ta-Nehisi Coates paints the story of conversion against a background of historical and cultural trauma, particularly the history of slavery. An authentic portrayal of the route to freedom for the main character Hiram Walker comes from a spiritual and physical liberation form. The interaction of freedom and spirituality is put into sharp relief by the introduction of Coates. The author through the use of sharp imagery depicts The Conduction as a supernatural mechanism of not only slavery's literal but also metaphorical escape facilitating awakening that checks across the group. *Freedom is a freedom to do things* - they get it through taking it, a power so strong only God can give. Hiram's journey to the liberation of his personality is not a physical one correct, but it is also very spiritual as he experiences his own inner screams and soldierings caused from his quest for inner peace. (Patterson, 2021: 162)

Spiritual Conversion in *The Water Dancer* is an idea based on liberation theology and one of the conceptions is that true freedom is leaving the oppressors

and be at peace with your soul. Coates, without shackling himself to any particular religious order, provides a dramatic demonstration of some of the theological issues of suffering, the redemption and the desire for transcendence. One or the other novel is about the process of changing faith, and yet, by the way, each of them departs quite oddly from the theme. Thanatos is a personification of the introduction or awareness of death, which often turns into soul-searching and the making of ethical decisions. As a result, the characters get to the stage of personal conversion. The individual's journey towards themselves is mainly due to existentialism, thus the theological concept that *conversion is an experience of the awareness of being mortal and limited* is emphasized. (Hayward, 2020: 91)

IV. Spiritual conflict and transformation: characters in crisis

Chloe Benjamin in *The Immortalists*, the underpinning therefore the spiritual conflict and transformation are the existential crises of the characters that can be the foundation for their flourish, therefore creating a unique masterful narrative in which she explores the spirituality of the characters. The story of the siblings is based on the prediction of their inevitable death which they knowingly and creatively act on to bring about individual but hazardous authentic journeys. Through their knowledge of their lives, the theological aspects of their lives are now realized based on their decisions, and also how they relate to fate, destiny, and free will. As the tangle of children attempts to come to terms with the mortality, Benjamin helps the reader to discover the deeper aspects of Christianity. The Christian existentialism, the search for meaning is the human act of trying to reconcile one's mortality with the possible timelessness of meaning. The divine plan and free will of humans are the central theme of the characters' spiritual developments as they undergo the pain of a negotiating existence that they cannot control beyond their understanding. (Shaw, 2021: 53)

The theological opposition in *The Immortalists* is a clear sense of the truth that life is a wider human condition that we need to reflect on how we can live truly and contentedly despite the fact that we have to deal with our mortality. In *The Water Dancer*, Ta-Nehisi Coates pastors an altogether newer but nevertheless deeply affecting version of spiritual conflict and its expression. Hiram Walker the protagonist is in a faith and identity conflict which is a result of the very fact that he is not just in the process of achieving physical freedom but also spiritual liberation. Coates actually juxtaposes Hiram's case of self-realization in the overall slavery and brutalization storylines as well, thus freedom fully not only physical but also a spiritual area of manifestation within the courses of history. The film shows the initial distance between Hiram and African Americans, as well as himself, which is a metaphor for the spiritual breakdown that has been experienced by many people in the context of systematic oppression. (Mitchell, 2019: 51)

During the storyline, however, Hiram finds spiritual truth through talks with metaphysical concepts in the novel, particularly, through the presence of conduction. This supernatural ability to travel out of remote

areas is suggested to be freedom that Hiram strives for as he communicates with his past and his ancestors, and finally, with his inner soul. It can be seen from the theological side that Hiram will now be in the process of liberating theology that shares the view that the emancipation process is not only political or social but mainly spiritual. His relatives' religion loses its meaning and through the new religious system of his life, he experiences God's free will and friendship through the truth he finds in himself and grounded interactions with his community. (Patel, 2021: 173)

The influence of spirituality on personal development in the novels is also demonstrated by the fact that they make the issues of spiritual conflict and personal identity visible and thus they tackle the complex issue of living a life that is not in sync with the spiritual reality. Both books present stories that correspond to the quests of the characters who are continuously driven by the desire to find the key to the riddle of their restless soul, the confrontation with the impending date of death or the battle for liberation from the bondage of slavery could be the case. On the one hand, spiritual growth is not the primary aim in any of these works, and on the other, it is a significantly transformative path that corresponds to the characters' level of understanding of self, fate, and faith. Spirituality as depicted in these novels is an aspect of the great human quest for existence that addresses issues like redemption and transcendence which provides a detailed analysis of how literature is related to theological themes and hence attracts the modern audience. (Brown, 2020: 44)

V. Mission and meaning: religious themes as social commentary

In *The Immortalists*, Chloe Benjamin creates a touching story that along with the main character, brings to light the broader issues of life and society. In their own ways, the siblings make the experiences of the knowledge of their eventual futures also the basis for their searches for truth that are deeper and more metaphorical and last longer when dealing with questions about fate, identity, and the human condition. The novel's leading theme is the personalization of the task which requires each character to find their own meaning in a life determined by both the known and the unknown. In their personal quest, the siblings' every little action (be it a relationship, career, or the choices made) turns into an actualization journey that gives them life meaning. (Davis, 2021: 173)

Through their personal experiences, the novel elucidates the interconnection of individual change to social commentary on free will, family, and the societal pressures that have a bearing on persons' lives. The religious elements in the story such as the search for redemption, faith, and spiritual resolution which are pertinent to contemporary readers who also confront their own questions about the meaning of life in an uncertain world. *The Immortalists* turns the tables on the human being's supposed destiny and poses this as an internal reaction to social phenomena, thus, a critique of the human desire to be the master of one's life. In *The Water Dancer*, Ta-Nehisi Coates sneaks the book to a level where religious and spiritual themes are slimmed all the

way to personal and common mission as tight as personal change around the thread of life. It is a story of Hiram Walker, a man who was born into slavery and has to resist cleverly both these material and spiritual chains, that frames the union of the mission and social change in the clearest way possible. Hiram's personal liberation is just as much about a whole and larger group that is striving to achieve the same as it is about an individual. The additional element of the story, *Conduction*, which enables Hiram to overtake his obstacles is a tool for his personal spirituality to rejuvenate, turning a good example of a possibility of personal change can lead to social change. (Fischer, 2019: 159)

Hiram sets a meaningful target that is incorporated in the Underground Railroad project, a collaborative effort that apart from giving cover to him, creates faith, resistance, and redemption. Additionally, Hiram's story is one that shows a forthcoming worldwide change by way of an elaborate network of underground activists, which Hiram gets the privilege to be a part of. Coates's skilful blending of individual and collective aspects in *The Water Dancer* gives the idea credence that spiritual rebirth should be shared which may inspire progressive justice and equality. (Schultz, 2021: 124)

Both *The Immortalists* and *The Water Dancer* bring forth the theme of mission in a way that it can evoke the religious and spiritual concerns of modern-day society. The Imaginarium project of the protagonists in *The Immortalists* becomes the de facto catalyst for them to come to grips with the stark reality of modern individualism, which is the only force left, in our culture, to guide them in that. This also conveys that the road to freedom from the rigid social roles of post-industrial times lies in the openness and outlying nature of the social relation. Equally, *The Water Dancer* contends that *the Spiritual renewal of an individual is intrinsically related to the community and is not merely a personal matter*, though the personal development and change in the group are taking place. Faith, fate as well as individual freedom issues are the topics of two novels that behove the reader to grasp the vital importance of the religious and spiritual world in the personal and social life of the human species, thus today even the most common societal problems can be solved. These books with their vibrant descriptions of the inner lives of the characters clearly show that the issues of faith and religion are still in the foreground of literature in that they provide new and fresh angles to the concept of a personal versus shared mission from the historical and social context. (Williams, 2021: 143)

VI. The impact of conversion: character arcs and theological development

In her book *The Immortalists*, Chloe Benjamin downplays the confined and exuberant picture of four physics majors in Manhattan engaged in escapism, but the ambiguous interpretation that people can achieve personal autonomy remains. Each of the siblings, knowing exactly the dates of their death, is transformed and their self-conception and place in the world is redefined. The due date, however, sucks them into the long-term effects of having knowledge of their deaths, predecessors of personal development, strife-tumult,

existential crises, repairing relationships, and redirecting their lives. An example is Simon, who is restless and is engaged with emancipation from the influence of societal expectations, and with experimenting with his sexuality. His conversion, however, can never be a transient one for he has to go through the long process of integrating who he is with who society wants him to be. Similarly, Klara's road trip is the one of spiritual and creative mutiny by getting meaning through her work as a magician; however, she is also wrestling with the limitations set by the past. (Robinson, 2020: 177)

The continual forge of their conversion exceeds the personal tracks and interacts with the dominant theme of the novel which deals with fate and freedom. The theological repercussions of the spiritual journeys of the characters are critiqued, and the concepts of redemption and salvation are put into a question mode, and it shows that conversion might not bring peace but rather a continuous inner inspection and self-discovery. Through these real-life character graphs, the author shows that conversion, both personal and spiritual, ultimately reforms their characters in a way that goes beyond them and affects their relationships with others and their understanding of life. *On the Water Dancer*, by Coates Ta-Nehisi unveils a powerful argument, the plot of spiritual conversion as an instrument of liberation from historical and generational trauma in the novel. The main character, Hiram Walker, comes through the experience of change and development in such a way that his personal freedom is linked to the freedom of the whole nation. Not only does Hiram's conversion religion get one's own conversion but his muscles of spiritual awakening and memory of ancestors. (Sullivan, 2020:102)

His discovery of his abilities, namely the mystical power of conduction, becomes a powerful symbol of his struggle toward freedom, physical and mental slavery, and the psychological wounds of inherited trauma as well. As Hiram learns how to use his powers, he also learns to break the chains that have tied him to his history and his place in the world. The time of spiritual conversion, as it is portrayed, not only the individual experience but also a whole is engaged act when Hiram's released potential affords him henceforth to participate in the underground railroad by force of enacting massed liberation movement. Hiram's spiritual conversion, in a way, is analogous to cutting the historical thread of slavery and thus escaping spiritual bondage. The novel proposes the usage of spiritual transformation to transcend traumatic situations, besides helping an individual, it can also be a kick-start for healing communities. Coates' portrayal of conversion is more about showing that the effect of such a change is not ephemeral but is a serious reshuffling of Hiram's role and identity in the context of the greater struggle for freedom. (Miller, 2020: 69)

Both *The Immortalists* and *The Water Dancer* embrace conversion as a mighty and earth-shattering phenomenon. In Benjamin's novel, the conversion inherently means stewing in the mixture of personal and psychological dilemmas by trying to predict the future and also the connection of religiousness to self-discovery that could be painful at the same time. However, in Coates' view, conversion is the only way to escape the

physical confines of the past, thus, he reconstitutes the old world and remakes the whole of society. The two novels, one via conversion as a process of change in the identities of the characters and, on the other side, through the questions of freedom, fate, and the possibility of redemption theologically reclaimed. The multiple and multi-layered characterizations of change that are dwelling in the different authors evoke the new realization that conversion might do more than just confuse people, it might even become a very invalidating experience for them when they look for the meaning and place of the Self through the social prism have been offered by this. The divine repercussions of these phenomena have gone as far as history and society, wherein they reflect the characters' lives. (Green, 2020: 188)

VII. Conclusion

The modern novel has metamorphosed the attitude toward mission and conversion, it has shifted from the traditional focus on the salvation of an individual to the more inclusive point of view exploring collective uplift and societal transformation. On the one hand, Chloe Benjamin's *The Immortalists* and Ta-Nehisi Coates' *The Water Dancer*, the idea of conversion is not only a personal way of redemption, but it also is an experience that is mutually felt and that formation is tied to broader societal changes. The heroes of these novels, who are in their own crises and, at the same time, are in search of meaning, co-operate with the larger communal and historical struggles that are at the same time the main story. This change is representative of the deeper theological issue that is the link between human experiences and the broader mission of healing and fixing the collective suffering and injustice. For example, in *The Water Dancer*, Hiram's spiritual transformation is a part of the entire nation's mission of emancipation, hence, in this way, it is shown that personal freedom can be seen as a process that is bound to the liberation of others.

The Immortalists is a similar case when it comes to the knowledge of one's fate which is the primary source of personal and relational dislocation, with each character's way of life corresponding to the subject of individual's role in the larger web of human existence. This newest approach to mission and conversion departs from the old theological framework, which concentrates on the individual soul's salvation only, and it instead presents a dynamic, relational view of man's existence. Both authors create a narrative of social and historical contexts in which spiritual transformation is relevant to underline that a mission that involves only personal redemption and lift-up of the individual only is no more possible; it has to be a collective phenomenon. The theological implications of these novels actually go much beyond the personal and thus they interrogate the moral and spiritual duties of individuals in relation to their communities. The process of conversion thus is a vehicle through which both personal and collective liberation is achieved and thus, it is a novel way in which mission could be depicted in contemporary fiction.

Besides, the theological investigation in *The Immortalists* and *The Water Dancer* also points out that it is still relevant to deal with spiritual and religious

themes in the contemporary literature. The novels present the constant need to deal with existential issues of meaning, identity, and the moral imperatives that guide human lives. The characters' endeavours for transformation, which are the timeless human struggles for the purpose in the face of loss, suffering, and historical oppression. Hence, they deal with those theological issues that are way beyond any one particular religious belief and provide a broader, more open-minded, and inclusive approach to the exploration of faith and spirituality. These works argue that despite the fact that the world is becoming more and more secular, literature is still a very important place to explore the human condition and the search for redemption. As these characters go through the ordeals of their time, their stories, which are about the universal craving for transformation and healing, become the works that are mandatory in the dialogue about mission, conversion, and the theological thought in contemporary fiction.

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